

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF BONDED JOINTS USING THE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Two and three dimensional nonlinear finite elements have been developed which are capable of accurately modelling the structural behavior of complex adhesive bonded joints. The elements are capable of modeling near-zero thickness bond lines without the numerical difficulties experienced by previous elements. They adequately represent the nonlinear material and physical characteristics that are typical of adhesive materials. This paper discusses the element formulation and presents numerical examples and a comparison with test data to validate the element performance.

KEYWORDS: Adhesives; Finite Element; Joint, bonded; Strength; Plasticity

1. INTRODUCTION

Adhesive bonded structures often have complex bondlines that are not amenable to mathematical characterization and must be analyzed using finite elements. A literature survey revealed that no finite element exists that has been specifically formulated to address the issues of adhesive joint analysis. The work of Hart-Smith (see for example, References 1 and 2), which has been the most widely used reference on the subject by design and analysis engineers, is restrictive in that it applies only to the analysis of relatively simple 2D lap joints. Other relevant work reported in the literature (Reference 3) is of a more academic nature and does not address the complexities inherent in general structural bondlines.

Use of current nonlinear finite elements suffer limitations in their ability to represent the material and geometric nonlinearities inherent in bonded joints. In order to accurately model adhesive joints, an element is required which can overcome the following limitations.

1.1 Inensitivity to Aspect Ratio The difficulty arises in that traditional elements must be very dense to capture the behavior of the bondline stress fields at or near free edges and singularities. Highly dense 'packing' of elements on the bondline requires that elements in adjacent structures must also be dense adjacent to the bond. Because of the general formulation of these elements, numerical instability occurs unless the aspect ratio of the elements is controlled to around 25:1 or less. (The aspect ratio is the ratio of the longest dimension of the element to the shortest dimension) Figure 1 shows a typical finite element

Figure 1 A typical finite element model of a 3D lap joint

model of a simple adhesive bondline application. In order to represent the thin bondline the analysis requires a large number of elements in both the bond and adjacent structure. The model size rapidly becomes unwieldy with just a small increase in the complexity of the joints. Since the problem is nonlinear the analysis computer run time can become prohibitive.

1.2 Large Deformations and Plasticity Typical adhesive materials are characterized by a relatively low shear modulus, low shear yield stresses, and a relatively high strain to failure. As a result adhesive bond layers deform well beyond their proportional limit (yield point) prior to failure. It has been observed that, as in the elastic range, this plasticity phenomenon is independent of the influence of the normal peel stresses. The present joint elements incorporate such a plasticity model which is substantially different from the ones used in the traditional nonlinear elements.

1.3 Temperature Dependent Material Characteristics The material properties of adhesives vary greatly as a function of temperature. The temperature dependence of the adhesive shear properties can be greater than a factor of 2, which is too large to be ignored for most applications.

2. ELEMENT FORMULATION

The formulation of the nonlinear two and three dimensional finite elements is described in detail in Reference 5, so only the key features are described here. First the three dimensional element formulation is discussed and the two dimensional modifications are then described. The element formulation essentially follows the conventional isoparametric approach. A typical 3D joint element is shown in figure 2. The element is an 8-noded hexahedron with 3 translational degrees of freedom per node. The formulation would be equally applicable to higher order elements, provided no mid-side nodes are present in the "thickness" direction.

FIGURE 2 Geometry of the 3D bonded joint element

Shown in Figure 2, X_i are the global Cartesian coordinates with the corresponding orthonormal base vectors, g_i . The element natural coordinates which range between -1 and $+1$ are denoted by ξ_j . The respective base vectors of ξ_j are, α_j . Also shown in Figure 2 is a set of right-handed orthogonal element local coordinate system z_i , with the corresponding base vectors, e_i . It is assumed that this local system is situated such that $(z_1 \ \& \ z_2)$ define the mid-plane of the joint and z_3 defines the thickness direction. In this presentation, tensor notation is to be used. Repeated indices imply summation, and the range of indices are 1-3, unless otherwise specified.

2.1 Element Stresses and Strains The element has the usual components of stress (σ_{ij}) and strain (ϵ_{ij}) tensors. The components, $(\sigma_{33}, \sigma_{13}, \sigma_{23})$, are the out-of-plane effects and $(\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12})$, are in-plane effects. The shear stresses in the bond line, σ_{13} and σ_{23} , together with the peel stresses, σ_{33} , are of primary concern in evaluating the strength of a bonded joint. In this development it is assumed that the in-plane and the out of plane effects are uncoupled. The in-plane stress and strains are assumed to be related through the usual plane stress relations for isotropic materials, i.e.

$$\{\sigma\}_1 = [C] \{\epsilon\}_1 \tag{1}$$

where

$$\{\sigma\}_1^T = \langle \sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12} \rangle ,$$

$$\{\epsilon\}_1^T = \langle \epsilon_{11}, \epsilon_{22}, \epsilon_{12} \rangle$$

and [C] is a 3x3 material modulus matrix which may include plasticity effects.

In the elastic range, the out of plane stress and strains are related through the following relation:

$$\{\sigma\}_2 = [D] \{\epsilon\}_2 \tag{2}$$

where,

$$\{\sigma\}_2^T = \langle \sigma_{33}, \sigma_{13}, \sigma_{23} \rangle$$

$$\{\epsilon\}_2^T = \langle \epsilon_{33}, \epsilon_{13}, \epsilon_{23} \rangle, \text{ and}$$

$$[D] = \begin{bmatrix} E & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & G & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

E and G are the elastic Young's and shear moduli of the adhesive material, respectively.

Following the reasoning of Hart-Smith (Ref 1), plasticity effects are considered only in the out-of-plane shear components. Therefore the shear and normal (peel stress) effects are uncoupled during the plastic deformation as they are in the elastic range. Thus, in the plastic range, a similar diagonal relation between the incremental stresses and strains, as shown in Equation (2), is assumed, except that in Equation (3) we replace G by G_T , the shear tangent modulus of the adhesive.

The element idealization is depicted in Figure 3. As shown, the element behavior is divided into two components: an in-plane component which may be represented by a conventional 2D isoparametric membrane element with thickness t, the adhesive thickness, and an out-of-plane component which may be idealized by a 3-dimensional assemblage of nonlinear springs K_s , and linear springs K_n as shown.

FIGURE 3 Element Idealization into in-plane and out-of-plane effects

2.2 Strain Displacement Relations The in-plane components of the incremental element strain tensor ($\epsilon_{11}, \epsilon_{22}, \epsilon_{12}$) are computed using the usual 2D strain displacement relations. The out-of-plane components,

(ϵ_{33} , ϵ_{13} , ϵ_{23}) at a given node, say k-th node, are computed using the following relations,

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{33}(k) &= (q_3(k+4) - q_3(k))/t_k \\ \epsilon_{13}(k) &= (q_1(k+4) - q_1(k))/t_k \\ \epsilon_{23}(k) &= (q_2(k+4) - q_2(k))/t_k \quad k=1,2,..,M \quad (M=\text{Number of nodes in element}/2) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In the above equations, q_1 is the nodal displacement and t_k is the element thickness at the k-th node, which is defined as

$$t_k = z_3(k+4) - z_3(k), \quad k=1,2,..,M \quad (5)$$

Here for simplicity, we assume that the element thickness is fairly constant and that its thickness, t , can be represented by an average of nodal thicknesses. It should be noted that in case the value of t drops below a threshold (say 1×10^{-5}), the formulation is such that, t can be set to unity and E and G in Equations (3) are then set respectively to pre-defined spring constants K_n and K_s as shown in Figure 3. The element can then be used to represent a 3D gap or surface contact element.

The out-of-plane strains at any location within the element may be interpolated using the nodal values, Equations (4), and 2D isoparametric interpolation functions.

2.3 Element Stiffness The nonlinear solution is obtained through an incremental approach. At the start of each load increment, the element geometry (nodal coordinates $\{z_1\}_n$) are updated and a new set of element kinematic and stiffness relations are computed. The tangent stiffness of the element, K_T , which relates the incremental nodal displacements to the incremental nodal forces is derived.

$$\{K_T\} = t \int_A [B]^T [D] [B] dA \quad (6)$$

$3N \times 3N$ $3N \times 3$ 3×3 $3 \times 3N$

Where $[B]$ is the incremental strain-displacement relation, $[D]$ is defined in Equation (3) and, dA is a differential area of the element mid-plane. The integral is evaluated numerically using the usual Gaussian quadrature points.

The equilibrium load vector, Q_e , of the element (due to the out-of-plane effects) which is used for computing the residual load vectors for iterative solution procedures is given below.

$$\{Q_e\} = t \int_A [B]^T \{\sigma\}_2 dA \quad (7)$$

$3N \times 1$ $3N \times 3$ 3×1

When assembling the structural stiffness matrix the tangent stiffness of the in-plane component is added to K_T (Equation 6) and the result transformed into the global coordinate system for assembly and factorization. Below, some special cases of this element are discussed.

2.4 Specialization to a Contact Element This element can easily be specialized into a zero-thickness 3D sliding contact or gap element by setting $t = 1.0$, $G = K_s$, and $E = K_n$ in Equations 3 and 6.

2.5 Specialization to a 2D Element A two dimensional version of this element (plane stress, plane strain, and axisymmetric) is shown in Figure 4. It is a 4 noded quadratic element ($N=4$) with local coordinates (z_1, z_2) and 2 translational degrees of freedom per node. The derivation proceeds along similar lines as described for the 3 D element. In terms of

Figure 4 Two Dimensional Bonded Joint Element

the element local system, the stress and strain components of interest for a bonded joint analysis are $(\sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12})$ and $(\epsilon_{22}, \epsilon_{12})$, where σ_{22} is the so called normal peel stress and σ_{12} is the shear stress in the 2D or axisymmetric adhesive layer.

The stresses and strains are evaluated at two locations within the element. Location 1 is at mid-point of nodes N1 and N4, and location 2 is at mid-point of nodes N2 and N3. The incremental strains are evaluated at these locations using the following strain displacement relations.

At location 1:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{22}(1) &= (q_2(4) - q_2(1)) / t \\ \epsilon_{12}(1) &= (q_1(4) - q_1(1)) / t \end{aligned} \tag{8a}$$

at location 2:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{22}(2) &= (q_2(3) - q_2(2)) / t \\ \epsilon_{12}(2) &= (q_1(3) - q_1(2)) / t \end{aligned} \tag{8b}$$

Where the pertinent node numbers are enclosed in the parentheses, and the node numbering convention for the element is shown in Figure 4.

As in the 3D version, a similar stress-strain relation is assumed

$$\{\sigma\} = [D] \{\epsilon\} \tag{9}$$

where $\{\sigma\}^T = \langle \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12} \rangle$, and

$$\{\epsilon\}^T = \langle \epsilon_{22}, \epsilon_{12} \rangle,$$

and [D] is a 2x2 diagonal material modulus matrix,

$$[D] = \begin{bmatrix} E & 0 \\ 0 & G \end{bmatrix} \tag{10}$$

with elastic E and elastic-plastic G (or G_T) similar to the 3D case. The stiffness matrix is computed in a manner entirely analogous to the three dimensional version. (See Reference 5) As with the three dimensional element, one can represent contact or gap elements by assigning zero thicknesses. Internally t is set to unity and E and G of the adhesive replaced by pre-defined spring constants K_n and K_s as shown in Figure 4.

3. ELEMENT VALIDATION

The two and three dimensional joint elements have been incorporated into the Lockheed developed program called NEPSAP⁶, which is a three dimensional nonlinear finite element code. The accuracy and reliability of the joint elements have been verified through a number of check cases whose solutions are compared with the available analytical results.

As an example, the single lap shear test specimen shown in Figure 5 is considered. The test specimen consisted of 1.6 mm thick 6061-T6 Aluminum fingers that were bonded using Hysol EA 9394 adhesive. The adhesive was cured at 250° F (121 °C). Six specimens were tested for tensile lap shear

Figure 5 The Single Lap Adhesive Bonded Joint Validation Analysis

strength per ASTM D1002. The failure of each specimen was a cohesive failure of the adhesive. The test results are:

Mean Failure load	9390 N	(2111 lb)
1-s Standard Deviation	1846 N	(415 lb)

3.1 Two Dimensional Plane Strain Model

Two NEPSAP finite element

models were constructed, a two dimensional plane strain model and a general

three dimensional solid model. Figure 6 shows schematically the two dimensional model that was used. The model consisted of 128 nodal points,

FIGURE 6 2-D Plain Strain Finite Element Model of Single Lap Joint

100 plain strain elements, with 247 displacement degrees of freedom. In order to simulate the 'jaws' of the test equipment, the nodes were restrained from relative angular rotation at each end. An incremental nonlinear solution procedure was employed in which 24 increments of the load 'P' were applied. The incremental load steps were of equal magnitude after the first increment which was completely elastic and linear.

FIGURE 7 Computed Adhesive Stresses & Strains at Predicted Failure load of 2050 lb (9119 N) Failure was considered to occur when the adhesive strain reached 0.15mm/mm. The bondline stress and strain distribution is shown in Figure 7. The

maximum strain was reached at 9119 N load. This is considered excellent agreement with the results of tests on 6 specimens (within 3%) which had an average failure load of 9390 N with a $1-\sigma$ standard deviation of 1815 N.

3.2 Three Dimensional Plane Strain Model A three dimensional finite element model of the single lap joint test specimen was constructed using 8-noded isotropic hexahedral elements to represent the adherends and 8noded elastic-plastic hexahedral bondline elements. The model had 288 node points, 140 elements, and 852 equations. A graphical representation of the model is shown in figure 8. Figure 9 shows the results obtained. The three dimensional model predicted a failure load of 10675 N (2400 lb). As can be seen by comparing the results shown in figures 7 & 9, the results for the 2D and 3D models are very similar. It should be noted that the model is not quite representative of the test specimens. The differences are that the adherend thickness was 2.54 mm instead of 1.6 mm, and the length of the adherends was 25.4 mm instead of 76.2 mm. These

FIGURE 8 FEM Model of Three Dimensional Adhesive Element Test Case

relatively small differences between the models account for the difference in predictions. However, the predicted failure at 10675 N is considered excellent agreement with the average test failure load of 9390 N with a $1-\sigma$ standard deviation of 1815 N.

4.0 CONCLUSIONS

Highly efficient and accurate elements have been formulated which significantly improve the ability to analyze the stress distribution in complex structural adhesive joints. The element formulation is based on accepted and proven theory and is capable of analyzing the near zero thickness typical of adhesive bond-lines without the numerical difficulties usually encountered by current elements. The elements have been

incorporated into the NEPSAP finite element computer program and their validity demonstrated by comparison of analysis and test results.

FIGURE 9 Computed Adhesive Stresses & Strains at Predicted Failure load of 2400 lb (10675 N)

5.0 REFERENCES

1. Hart-Smith, L. J., "Adhesive Bonded Double Lap Joints," NASA, CR-112235, January, 1973.
2. Hart-Smith, L. J., "Adhesive Bonded Single Lap Joints," NASA, CR-112236, January, 1973.
3. Aviazadeh S. and Verchery G., "Stress Analysis at the Interface in the Adhesive Joints by Special Finite Elements," International J. of Adhesion and Adhesives, Vol 6, No 4, pp 185-188, 1986.
4. Goodman R.E., et al, "A Model for the Mechanics of Jointed Rock," J of Soil Mech, Proc ASCE, Vol 94, No. SM3, May 1968, pp 637-659.
- ✓ 5. Sharifi, P and Sable, W., "A Nonlinear Joint Element for the Analysis of Adhesive Bonded Joints," AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC 32ND SDM Conference, April, 1991
- ✓ 6. LMSC-D556019, "NEPSAP, Nonlinear Elastic-Plastic Structural Analysis Program," User's Guide for NEPSAP, Sep 1989.

6.0 BIOGRAPHY

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